

EFFECTIVE METHODS FOR ENHANCING LINGUISTIC PROFICIENCY IN ENGLISH

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Abstract. *Fundamentally, a lexical approach to teaching entails placing the main emphasis on assisting students in acquiring language. This article explores the concept of lexical abilities, including their structure, characteristics, and the stable conditions necessary for their development. It also discusses the sequential process involved in acquiring new lexical units. All of these factors must be considered during the process of acquiring vocabulary in a foreign language. The author examines useful exercises that enhance and cultivate students' lexical skills in the English language.*

Keywords: *lexical exercise, teaching materials, foreign language teaching, vocabulary improvement.*

Currently, the primary goal of educational institutions is to enhance the overall quality of the educational process and the efficacy of foreign language instruction. In the 20th century, various fields of study such as methodology, didactics, linguistics, and psychology were dedicated to tackling a set of interconnected issues, with the primary concern being the challenge of teaching foreign languages to pupils of varying ages and educational backgrounds.

An essential approach to addressing educational challenges is the issue of language acquisition. Acquiring a strong vocabulary requires a targeted approach, as certain phrases and words are more easily committed to memory, while others require particular exercises designed to enhance the recall process.

The practice of learners in acquiring new words is achieved through exercises aimed at developing and enhancing their lexical productivity. All exercises related to its structure can be categorized into two groups: exercises that concentrate on memorizing the words, their meaning in conjunction with their pronunciation and grammatical form, leading to the retrieval of words from long-term memory, and exercises aimed at reinforcing the syntagmatic and paradigmatic relationships of lexical units.

The acquisition of vocabulary occurs through the assimilation of its form and meaning in relation to specific situations and the necessity of expressing thoughts and emotions. Following the presentation, initial instruction in the use of new words is conducted through conditional-speech exercises, which involve imitating, substituting, transforming, and reproducing language in a carefully structured interactive setting. These activities are supplemented with a unit focused on communication.

Simulation training enables students to generate sensory experiences through the auditory and visual representation of words, which are linked to the motor skills involved in speech production. This facilitates the long-term retention of the formal aspects of speech. Equally significant, as stated by Filatov V.M., is the recognition of the significance and intention of words in their cohesion, as well as the connection between the word (the aural representation) and its

purpose and objective [2]. Wildcard exercises enhance the connections between words and promote the development of associative recall.

The communicative and practical objective of teaching foreign languages in high school can be achieved through three language categories, which can help decrease the diversity of activities:

1. **Not communicative exercises** – these activities are conducted to enhance comprehension and deliberate absorption of linguistic elements (such as grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation) across many forms of speech. The exercises encompass the following:

- 1) Linguistic or facet:
 - a) Grammatical aspects, such as ensuring the verb is correctly conjugated;
 - b) Lexical aspects, such as substituting words with appropriate meanings and grouping words by topic;
 - c) Phonetic aspects, such as pronouncing numerical words correctly and grouping words by their pronunciation patterns.

These activities are utilized as homework throughout the appropriate phase of studying the content.

2) Transformation exercises involve modifying affirmative statements into interrogative or passive forms.

3) Translation exercises are utilized for control purposes.

4) Imitative, wildcard tasks involve expanding a lexical unit inside a specific structure or creating phrases using words provided in various columns.

2. Speech exercises or communicative exercises

The objective of these activities is to use the communicative functions of a foreign language and instruct communication skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

Speech exercises are inherently imaginative activities. The tasks are consistently characterized by meaningful discourse at various levels. The primary attributes of exercises are pragmatism and motivation, which involve encouraging initiative and motivating students [6].

Passov E.I and Kuznetsova E.E. categorize these exercises into three classes [1]:

1) Content rendering exercises include retelling, short selective essays, retelling-translation, dramatization, and other similar exercises.

2) Description exercises involve describing elementary images, feature stories, and real objects.

3) Expression exercises focus on expressing attitudes and evaluations through discussions and comments.

These activities are designed to simulate conversation and enable individuals to operate efficiently and easily by following a specific way of execution. Naturally, they can communicate through speech; their approach can be characterized by a certain methodology. Examples include exercises including statements, conditional conversations, students' inquiries, press conferences, interviews, and exercises such as "contact me".

3. Conditional-speech exercises or conditionally communicative exercises

This sort of exercise is characterized by its ability to facilitate the practice of language material in educational or simulated communication settings that mimic natural language use.

Conditional-speech exercises ought to be contextual, meaning that the teacher's statement and the student's response should pertain to the specific circumstance, the relationship between the participants, and their ongoing actions. It is imperative for them to guarantee that the students

prioritize the aim and content of the statements rather than the form. The statements should be characterized by their communicative value, as the students are in the process of learning.

The teacher should refrain from making unsubstantial comments such as "Confirm that you are engaging in the same activity: - I wear a coat in the winter." "During the winter season, I don a coat." One should consider the efficacy of the exercises in terms of time.

Categories of conditional-speech exercises: The student engages in imitative behavior by completely replicating the teacher's remark. In these exercises, a substitution of lexical units is employed within a receiving structure. Transformation involves altering perceived forms, such as converting passive voice to active voice. Reproduction occurs when the assimilated form is generated based on self-perception.

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